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Keyphrase Extraction And Source Code Similarity Detection- A Survey

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Abstract. Keyphrase extraction is the starting phase of feature extraction and many other NLP tasks. Hence, keyphrase extraction ensures the separation of essential and relevant information from the rest of the document or corpus. A similarity score is used for detecting similarities between two or more documents. In this paper, a summary of existing research conducted in the field of keyphrase extraction and source code similarity detection is presented. The literature focuses on more concept-based research instead of going towards the domain level. There exist a promising potential for the creation of recommendation systems by employing similarly situated research techniques.

Keywords: *Software Engineering, Keyphrase Extraction, Text Mining, Similarity calculation, Source Code Analysis*

1. Introduction

Keyphrase Extraction (KE) involves getting the essential and relevant words from a given document or a text [1]. It forms an important component of Text Mining which involves various tasks on the text at hand. The field of text mining also has linkage to Natural Language Processing/Computational Linguistics (CL) which entails the usage of text / speech in completing various tasks. The field of KE finds close application with Information Retrieval, Information Storage, and other such related fields.

Keyphrase or words constitute different types of both print and electronic medium. Whenever there is a presence of text in the form of words, sentences, paragraphs, the role of keyword extraction can come into play. As a result of this, Keyphrase extraction is extensively used in following [22] [30]:-

- Text Classification
- Text Clustering
- Document summarization
- Web mining
- Concept Extraction
- NLP/CL

- Information Retrieval
- Feature Extraction

Source Code Analysis (SCA) forms the basis for program understanding and comprehension. The developers as well the system maintainers are tasked with understanding the source code of the created projects owing to following reasons:

- Reassigned to a new location
- Resource crunch
- New projects assigned to the team.

SCA can also aid in the development of a recommendation system for the developer all its allied roles.

These include testers, maintenance engineers in developing a better understanding of the software product. Similarity detection finds its application in source code analysis for detecting duplicate codes or plagiarism. Figure-1 gives different types of existing source code , based on similarity detection techniques [44].

Figure-1 Source Code based Similarity Measures [44].

Token-based approaches are further categorized into single or N-gram according to the size of tokens [8].

Tree-based approaches make use of Abstract Syntax Tree which is part of the model construction phase of SCA. AST helps in detecting location-specific codes within two files. Semantic-based Graph source code similarity measures ignore the programming language constructs. Graph-based approaches can manage minor changes to the source code but have higher complexity as compared to other approaches. Graph-based approaches are further classified as Program-Dependence-Graph and Control-Flow-Graphs. Compiled code-based approaches don't require source code for computing similarity. Model-based approaches detect duplicity in models [8].

Figure 2: KE Extraction Techniques [2]

Keyphrase extraction consists of supervised, unsupervised and semi-supervised research techniques.

Keyphrase Extraction Models

There are following types of keyphrase extraction models which are present in the literature:

1. TF-IDF
2. Kea
3. TopicRank
4. SingleRank
5. PageRank
6. TextRank
7. ExpandRank [16] [21]

2. Literature Review on Keyphrase Extraction & Similarity-Based Source Code Analysis

2.1. Literature Review of Survey Papers

In the course of undertaking literature survey of the survey papers, following papers came into limelight [1][2][3][4][5][6][17]:-

“An Overview of Graph-Based Keyword Extraction Methods and Approaches” [2]

The authors, in this work, provide an introduction to Keyphrase Extraction basics. The authors provide a classification of KE methods research. This is followed by the categorization of keyphrase extraction techniques. The paper provides a strong mathematical base for graph-based keyword extraction research. The literature review section of the paper provides a paragraph explanation focusing mainly graph on KE techniques [2]. The paper also discusses categories of literature reviews discussed along with the different categories of the KE techniques.

“Automatic keyphrase extraction: a survey and trends” [17]

The paper by Zakariae et. al. provides a major review on the current existing state-of-art research on Automatic Keyphrase Extraction (APKE). The paper also provides different future research directions along with future trends for the prospective researchers [17].

2.2. Literature Review of Keyphrase Extraction papers

Wei et. al. mention employing knowledge graphs for providing semantic relations for keyphrase extracted in the KE task. The authors also provide a framework for combining clustering and graph ranking for the same task of KE. As a result, the author gets better results when compared to traditional approaches [8].

Santhi et. al. propose developing information by using relationships between elements in a graph [9].

Dario et. al. develop an automatic curator system for the purpose of scholarly data access tools. In order to accomplish this, various tools and methods have been employed from the varied fields of CL, cloud, user modeling, and information retrieval [11].

Sujatha et. al. use the following techniques in keyphrase taggers in research papers:-

1. linguistics
2. surface form
3. document-structure

The created tagger is trained with conditional random fields which gives results in consonance with the existing work. In addition, by implementing the feature extraction technique, the system performance increased [12].

Nesi et. al. present a distributed framework for the purpose of running NLP computations and tasks. GATE API is used and build upon the Hadoop platform. The evaluation includes using the real-world corpus of web pages. The framework proposed is distributed as well as parallel environments [13].

Teng-li et al. make use of an unsupervised approach for conducting graph-based ranking and clustering within-collection resources. The graph-based ranking describes significance in-between two words. The topic-based clustering introduces additional linguistic information in words. The clusters assign the right meaning to the appropriate word [18].

Guoxiu He et.al. discuss a keyphrase extraction technique that employs prior knowledge for the extraction of keyphrase from the document. Authors develop a controlled vocabulary using existing document collections in the keyphrase collection phase. Prior probability is used to highlight the need of using TF-IDF and Text Rank jointly. The optimal weights are learned using the machine learning's supervised algorithm. Experimental results convincingly show the benefit of employing prior probability for KE [20].

Niraj et. al. propose N-gram filtration method in KE. This is accomplished by using the statistical features and also the co-location strength. Statistical features imply using the centrality scores of words for checking the border nodes. In addition, the N-gram graph is also generated [21].

Dhruva et.al. created a tool named BiLSTM-CRF. Keyphrase extraction is done as a labelling task. This represents input text in form of contextualized embedding. For evaluation contextualized and fixed word embedding models are used. For comparison, the authors make use of supervised & unsupervised approaches [23].

Santosh et. al. have developed a tool named DAKE. This tool conducts keyphrase extraction at the document level by using BLSTM [24].

Tianlei et. al. propose developing keyphrases by classifying the candidate keyphrases in different categories using graph-based attributes and non-graph-based attributes [25].

Ankit et al address two major issues concerning keyphrase extraction. These include candidate selection for the keyphrase extraction and extraction of necessary features. The authors use a supervised ML algorithm for keyword extraction. For evaluation purpose, SingleRank, TFIDF, Expand Rank is used [26].

Corina et. al. propose a new scoring measure for phrases for calculating the final scores by averaging out the individual words weighted by the frequency of phrases [28].

Keyphrase or keyword extraction or searching also finds its relevance in spatial objects databases and software testing [11] [29]. This is mainly due to the textual nature of the artifacts produced.

SKEM methodology proposed by authors generates graphs based on the semantics of keywords by making use of different centrality measures. The source for keywords extraction is the twitter data. The top ten words are chosen based on ranking and nodes score calculations [31].

Linkal et. al. have devised an unsupervised algorithm for keyphrase-extraction. Authors proposed making use of structural and the semantic information of the document in the process of keyphrase extraction. After creating the graph consisting of potential keywords, the weights are calculated using the relative distance between candidate keyphrases [32].

Mauro et. al. developed Crank approach which uses an unsupervised approach to extract keyphrases from documents. The heuristics and centrality measures are used in assigning weights to the graph [33].

Gollam et. al. proposes TeKET technique which uses lesser statistical knowledge and needs no prior training. The authors also propose a Keyphrase based tree for final candidate selection and an index (CI) for measuring nodes cohesion wrt root [34].

Zheng et. al. develop knowledge graphs through which key phrases can be extracted. The technique finds the latent relationships between two key-terms using knowledge graphs [35].

Swagata et.al. develop a framework for extracting keywords. The complex network developed is used for extracting features. Node properties are used to differentiate between keywords and non-keywords [38].

D. Sowmya et al. use swarm optimization techniques in keyphrase extraction. The process followed includes keyword extraction, clustering of the keyphrases. The process uses intervention at every stage [40].

In the current section, a literature review based on UML diagrams generation, keyphrase extraction, and clustering are discussed. Table-1 gives a comparative analysis of research papers related to UML diagram construction.

Table 1. Literature Review of existing work on Keyphrase Extraction

Reference number	Title of Paper	Advantage of Proposed Work	Disadvantages of Proposed Work
8	A New Multi-lingual Knowledge-base Approach to Keyphrase Extraction for the Italian Language	Authors propose creating a multi-lingual tool for extracting keyphrases of English and Italian language	Authors did not consider keyphrase extraction for different languages. Keyphrase generation can be extended for other languages also.
10	Knowledge-Based Techniques for Scholarly Data Access: Towards Automatic Curation	The authors propose a system that is useful for researchers by using data mining, NLP, clustering, Graph-based approaches.	This is a major project & needs multiple domain level experts for its proper execution
12	A Distributed Framework for NLP-Based Keyword and Keyphrase Extraction From Web Pages and Documents	The authors use keyphrase-extraction in cloud based systems. GATE architecture is employed on cloud. The web crawler is also integrated into the system	The more testing of GATE based applications can be done. Hadoop implementation can also be extended
13	Building a Construction Project Key-Phrase Network from Unstructured Text Documents	For unstructured text, authors propose document management system, project keyphrase network, support libraries & system for civil engineering projects	The current work can be extended for contextual awareness, interactive interface and controlled vocabulary
14	Identifying Candidate Tasks for Robotic Process Automation in Textual Process Descriptions	Authors identify & classify tasks using BPMN for textual processes	In practice textual descriptions are not the same as provided in the paper.
15	Simple Unsupervised Keyphrase Extraction using Sentence Embeddings	Authors make use of EmbedRank, to extract keyphrases from single document. The unsupervised ML algorithm is used for the process. Sentence embedding is employed in the process.	Unsupervised approach may introduce biasing due to inherit noise in the document.
16	How Document Pre-processing affects Keyphrase Extraction Performance	Authors reassess the performance of five keyphrase extraction models and conclude that document pre-processing affects performance.	More keyphrase extraction models such as ExpandRank, SingleRank can be used for assessment.
18	An Unsupervised Approach for Keyphrase Extraction Using Within-Collection Resources	Authors use graph-based ranking for checking relevance across the words. The topic-based cluster for the purpose of semantic enrichment.	The work is restricted to only scholarly documents
20	Keyphrase Extraction Based on Prior Knowledge	Authors make use of controlled vocabulary, prior-probability & supervised ML for Keyphrase Extraction	None mentioned

21	A graph-based unsupervised N-gram filtration technique for automatic keyphrase extraction	Authors used ngram approach for candidate selection and ranking of candidate keyphrases.	As resources become multilingual, it is possible to extend the authors work.
22	Feature selection, optimization and clustering strategies of text documents	Authors provided a review of clustering and its allied research areas including similarity measures. Authors conclude text clustering research focussed on dynamic & Heterogeneous clustering applications	Community-driven clustering could not be addressed in the given literature.
23	Keyphrase extraction as sequence labeling using contextualized embeddings	Authors make use of BiLSTM-CRF ML technique architecture for keyphrase extraction and including embedding the context.	The authors work can be extended to keyphrase generation
24	DAKE: Document-Level Attention for Keyphrase Extraction	Authors makes use bi-directional LSTM which extracts keyphrases from documents.	The source documents are not multilingual
25	A Graph-Based Keyphrase Extraction Model with Three-Way Decision	Authors propose a three way categorization of candidate phrases before undertaking graph-based clustering	None mentioned

2.3. Literature Review of Research papers Related to Source Code Analysis Based Similarity Index

Recent research in applying Deep Learning to Source Code Analysis deals with using program vector representation. The authors conclude that Deep Learning cannot be applied directly to Back Propagation Networks. Hence, alternatively, code criterion forms the basis of building program representations. The authors also check the studying programming by deep NN. The methodology entails defining granularity at the character, token, AST, statement levels [45].

Plagiarism in source code is a major problem. Hence, its detection provides several research directions. TF-IDF is traditional metrics employed in the field of text mining. Author's hence proposed applying this measure to source-code files. The methodology divides the program into language dependent tokenizes and language-specific indexes [46].

Code similarity calculation finds its application in online architecture and comparison. Some of the source code similarities and general similarities are discussed. The methodology is divided into program collection, candidate selection, plagiarism detection, and in-depth discussion [47].

Binary code similarity identifies similar or identical code segments in binary programs. The authors state that the semantic-based code has varied issues on source code. Hence, the authors propose a hybrid-method to compare binary similarity tools named BinMatch. This tool captures the semantic aspects of binary function both dynamically and statistically. Binmatch's proposed methodology includes test cases, target function, and similarity computation[48].

In academics, similarity calculation has been applied to undertake evaluation and ranking of students. Authors propose the creation of examples using intelligent hypertext. The ontology is employed in the extraction of necessary concepts from examples using similarity calculation. In order to do content enrichment, structural & non-structural approaches are proposed to be used [49].

The lexical or tokens based similarity for been proposed by the authors for short sentences to undertake granularity evaluation. Authors employ on the string of code, Levenstein distance, cosine similarity, hamming distance, ASCII-based hashing, and Round-Karp rolling. Rabin Karp performs better than all others for different repositories size [50].

SCA also has been used to aid the identification of class-errors and to create a recommendation system for giving feedback to users. Similar codes provide assessment criteria to measure common

properties. The authors propose code plagiarism detection as the first step & cluster creation as the second step in the methodology [51].

SCA also finds its applicability in clone detection for large scale online repositories. Authors propose a technique called OCD which serves the purpose of code similarity as well as code clone searching [52].

The author presents code-clone detection as an application of SCA. Two different metrics introduced compare program features and control statement. The author's work can be summarized as project code metrics calculation and using these metrics for similarity calculation [53].

SCA has also been in the generation of comments for the existing codes. The tool developed named CloCom uses detection techniques to discover code segments and use their comments in describing codes having a similar theme [54].

Song et. al. compute the similarity between two source codes. Convolution Kernel-function is employed for the ultimate aim of plagiarism detection among a pair of codes [55].

Ivan et. al. use string complexity and compression in source code plagiarism detection. Kolmogorov complexity is employed for computing similarity measures. The authors provide a comparative analysis of the calculated similarity with synthetic benchmarks [56].

Traceability between SDLC artifacts forms a major concern for the IT industry. Hence, Amir et. al. present a language-independent link for connecting source code to requirement documents. The methodology employed entails feature extraction from documents and source code, completion of abbreviation through similarity measure, and using data mining technique to find linkages between documents and source code [57].

In the area of code smell detection, centrality measures are often employed. These include measures such as Euclidean distance being used with Genetic-Algorithm & particle swarm optimization. The code smells are detected by computing the similarity between the systems. The approach detects BLOB, Functional Dependencies, spaghetti code, Data Class, and feature envy. The authors also categorize similarity detection literature as search-based non-search based and model-based code smell detection techniques [58].

Firas et. al. present an approach for detecting similar code snippets based on graph fingerprinting. The methodology proposed first creates graphs from source code. The generated graphs are used for creating unique fingerprinting of the code [59].

Oscar et. al. summarize different source code-based similarity detection techniques research papers. Authors categorize the submitted source code similarity detection technique into structural, non-structural, and hybrid approaches [60].

Zhongehen et. al. develop a structural similarity measure for the representation of UML Class Graph. Similarity calculated is both intra-structural as well as inter-structural. These measures are claimed to be useful for software reuse [61].

Table 2 Advantage and disadvantage of Research Papers on Source Code Analysis Based on Similarity Detection & Code Smell

Reference Number	Title of Paper	Advantage Research of Paper	Disadvantage/Future Scope of Research Paper
45	Building Program Vector Representations for Deep Learning	Author applied vector representations to code analysis.	DL can be applied to complete domain of SCA.
46	TF-IDF Inspired Detection for Cross Language Source Code Plagiarism and Collusion	The author applied vector representations to code analysis. DL can be applied to complete domain of SCA	Identifier renaming disguise to be done based on first occurrence.
47	A Scalable Code Similarity Detection with Online Architecture and Focused Comparison for	Cosine similarity introduced by the authors reduces lead to short running time especially with large token strings.	The techniques proposed can be proposed for some other programming courses as well.

	Maintaining Academic Integrity in Programming		
48	BinMatch: A Semantics-Based Hybrid Approach on Binary Code Clone Analysis	A hybrid method for comparing binary similarity. Evaluation of methodology done on nine real-world projects.	Methodology can be extended for 64-bit system as well.
49	A study of concept-based similarity approaches for recommending program examples	RS system developed aids in the understanding of the student.	RS system based on other ideas can be developed
50	Assessing lexical similarity between short sentences of source code based on granularity	Differed measures of source code compared and Rabin–Karp rolling hashing is suggested as the best.	Rabin–Karp rolling hashing can be applied to open source software's as well.
51	Automatic programming error class identification with code plagiarism-based clustering	Authors provide a clique of offline analysis error detection and on-the-fly learners feedback.	Different datasets can be used for experimentation can be used such as code-hunt data sets.
52	Code similarity and clone search in large-scale source code data	The thesis discusses the technique for a dual methodology of calculating code similarity and providing clone searching on large code data. OCD and Siamese are tools developed.	Clone direction detection can be automated. New services in cloud-based environments can be given to developer.
53	Code similarity detection through control statement and program features	The proposed methodology is evaluated on C projects of Bellon's benchmark dataset and student lab programs (SLP)	Control Statement can be included in the proposed methodology.
54	CloCom: Mining existing source code for automatic comment generation	Automation in source code comments is achieved.	Yield & Accuracy can be improved by the proposed methodology.
55	Computation of program source code similarity by composition of parse tree and call graph	For Java-based source code plagiarism detection, the proposed method performs better than existing systems. The proposed work can be used for C, C++, Python.	Centrality measures can be included in this work.
56	Detecting Source Code Similarity Using Compression.	Similarity detection is done based on Kolmogorov complexity	Consideration of base code forms the part of the future assignment.

The literature review indicated that for Keyphrase extraction for various natural languages has been conducted. These include English, Arabic, Persian languages [39].

3. Evaluation of System Developed

There are following metrics which are used in keyphrase extraction research:-

1. Preference measure (bpref)
2. Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR)
3. Precision
4. Recall
5. F-measure [4]

Suitable datasets were also chosen according to the domain of work for evaluation purposes. Keyphrase extraction can also be applied to various phases of SDLC and its artifacts. These include SRS, SDS, Testing artifacts, source code, and maintenance phases [29]. Keyphrase extraction also finds its applicability in clustering approaches and plagiarism detection and

similarity calculation [37] [41]. Software Engineering has been applied at the subject level in various domains [43]. Keyphrase Extraction can be applied however at the topic level.

4. Recommendation System

Table 3 Keyphrase-based RS versus Source Code Based RS

Keyphrase-Based RS	Source Code-Based RS
Part of a Larger System including Source Code- based RS	Specific to Source Code
Addressed for larger audience	Addressed for specific audience
Domain-level concepts can be addressed	Domain-level concepts can be addressed

Recommendation Systems (RS) are useful to various stakeholders across SDLC. The systems can aid in quick decision making by providing insights to the changes being made to system at large. Table-IV shows the comparison of keyphrase-Based RS and source code-based RS. The artifacts of SDLC are developed by different stakeholders [62]. RS system can be developed for addressing the common needs of the stakeholders.

5. Conclusion

In the current work, an effort is made to summarize the existing state-of-art work in the field of Keyphrase Extraction and similarity measure based source code analysis. Keyphrase extraction is more related to the pre-processing stage of Source Code Analysis. Similarity measures denote a statistical term of measurement of any file based parameter. The future scope presented for the research papers can be used for conducting future research.

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